

Accessibility Options

Changing the
general
appearance to
improve
accessibility

Existing options

Using these options makes
me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Accessibility Options

Adding audio features to improve accessibility

Existing options

Using these options makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Accessibility Options

Using zoom or magnifying features to improve accessibility

Existing options

Using these options makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Accessibility Options

Using images to improve accessibility

Existing options

Using these options makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Accessibility Options

Using voice control
to improve
accessibility

Existing options

Using these options makes
me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

